

Multiuser Sparse Vector Code based Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication for Intelligent Transportation Systems

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Abstract—Intelligent transportation systems (ITS) often involve the transmission of short packets with specific requirements for low latency and high reliability. Short packet transmission scheme such as sparse vector coding (SVC) is a primary candidate that offers ultra-low latency and high-reliability communication (URLLC). This paper proposes a spectral-efficient multiuser SVC (MU-SVC) scheme for achieving URLLC. The key idea is to transmit a superimposed SVC signal created from the far users (FU) and near users (NU) data. Firstly, the FU binary data is converted into a sparse vector and secondly, the NU data is modulated and embedded into the non-zero positions of the sparse vector to form an MU-SVC. On transmission, the FU and NU decode their information through compressed sensing-based support detection. The FU data is obtained through sparse demapping, while the NU adopts symbol detection techniques like the maximum likelihood detector. A new performance metric, called position error rate (PoER), is introduced to study the performance of the FU since it is based on the correct identification of the non-zero positions. Theoretical analyses of PoER and symbol error rate (SER) were carried out for FU and NU, respectively and the results are also validated through Monte-Carlo simulations. Further, the bit error rate, complexity, spectral and latency analyses are performed for MU-SVC and compared with the SVC and enhanced SVC schemes. Also, the significance of PoER metric is analyzed for specific transmit signal-to-noise ratio and its relevance to performance is discussed. The simulation results demonstrate an improved spectral efficiency and low latency with high reliability for the proposed MU-SVC scheme, thus, achieving URLLC with reduced complexity in the multiuser scenario for ITS.

Index Terms—Multiuser, position error rate, sparse vector coding, superimposed transmission, symbol error rate, URLLC

I. INTRODUCTION

ULTRA-reliable and low-latency communication (URLLC) is gathering keen attention in 5G and beyond (5GB) wireless systems due to an increase in time-critical and round-the-clock accessible applications. URLLC is designed to deliver communication services with extremely high levels of reliability. This is crucial for

applications where even a small amount of packet loss or communication failure could have serious consequences, such as in industrial automation, remote surgery, autonomous vehicles, and public safety scenarios [1]–[3]. URLLC plays a crucial role in the context of intelligent transportation systems (ITS), where vehicles, infrastructure, and other elements need to communicate quickly and reliably to ensure safety and efficiency [4], [5]. Moreover, most of the applications require only tiny information to transmit such as moving forward/backward, turning left/right, on/off, etc., (control signals) and hence demand efficient transmission control. Short packet transmission is a key enabler of URLLC which addresses the need for both low latency and reliable data transmission in applications that require real-time interactions and critical reliability, making it a fundamental aspect of modern wireless communication systems. The benchmark for URLLC is 99.99% reliability with less than 1ms latency and one in a million block error rate (BLER) [6]–[11]. In par with this, sparse vector coding (SVC) is proposed in [12] for transmission of short packets to achieve URLLC. The idea is to explore the sparse nature of the information and get rid of conventional channel coding schemes which require lengthy codes with complex nature [12]–[15]. In SVC, the information is sparsely mapped with the minimum number of non-zero elements and pseudo-randomly spread through a code book (dictionary matrix) at the transmitter. This information is then transmitted over the channel and at the receiver the signal is considered to be undetermined. To address this, compressed sensing (CS) based sparse recovery algorithms (SRA) are aided for successful decoding of the information. A probability of success analysis is carried out and shows that SVC supports URLLC. Likewise in [12]–[17], BLER analysis is performed for SVC with various parameters which depend on less pilot overload and pilot-less transmission. Recently, an enhanced SVC (ESVC) scheme is proposed for URLLC in which the information is encoded as symbols in addition to position for enhancing the reliability [18]. At the receiver, the support is identified through SRA, and symbols are detected by conventional techniques. From the performance analysis, it is depicted that SVC is less efficient than ESVC. Likewise, SVC for massive multiple input and multiple output (MIMO) is proposed in [19] which transmits information through multi antenna system. At the receiver, successive cancellation is carried out to decode the

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intended user information. Moreover, SVC is exploited with multicarrier non-orthogonal multiple access (MC-NOMA) for in-home health networks [20] in which the inter carrier interference (ICI) suppression is achieved due to sparse nature of the information transmitted. To further enhance the performance of SVC, the constellation group based rotation technique is adopted in [21] which maps the information bits to sparse vectors ensuring that the minimum Euclidean distance between the constellation is large. Likewise in [22], [23] sparse superimposed transmission (ST) is exploited for SVC in which a certain amount of information is sparsely mapped and the remaining part of the information is mapped to non-zero positions through constellation rotation. Simulation results show that the SVC-ST scheme performance is superior in terms of BLER. Furthermore, to enhance the reliability, ESVC with the limited pilot overhead is explored in which the sparse vector is scaled by the fading channel and decoding does not require any channel state information [24]. Likewise, the sparse vector is composited with maximal ratio transmission over the channel for enhancing the reliability of the system in [25]. Furthermore, to enhance the performance of SVC, a superimposed transmission technique is adopted in [26]. The encoding is done by sparse mapping a certain part of user information into non-zero sparse vector and remaining part is quadrature amplitude modulated through constellation rotation. In addition, SVC is also aided for integrated sensing and communication applications [27] for enhancing the reliability and attenuating the side lobes of radar signals. The information is sparse mapped and the control for reducing the side lobes of the radar signal are embedded into the spreading code, thus ensuring reliability with lower lobes for radar sensing. An optimized code book or resource element is utilized in [28] for spreading the sparse vector to enhance the reliability, reduce complexity and hardware realization in URLLC applications. Also, outage analysis of SVC is carried out for MC-NOMA in [29] and shown that SVC aids for suppressing the ICI in multi-carrier communication and contributes for URLLC. Yet importantly, SVC is exploited for high mobility scenario with Doppler effect in [30] which accounts the time varying channel parameters. The data and the pilots for estimating the time varying channel is sparse mapped at the transmitter which is then pseudo randomly spread over a random spreading code. At the receiver, the decoding of data by canceling out the pilots is performed through iterative interference cancellation and the channel is estimated by iterative data-aided process.

URLLC in the context of ITS can enable a variety of applications and services. To mention a few, vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication, traffic management, infrastructure monitoring, remote vehicle control, emergency services, cooperative adaptive cruise control, etc. Moreover, ITS involves transmission of information from multiple devices/users for creating a comprehensive, integrated, and user-friendly transportation system. In applications such as autonomous vehicles and truck platooning, the amount of information transferred is petite but the number of devices/users connected is large and demands for spectrum efficient communication. Also, in modern automated applications, more

TABLE I
LIST OF SYMBOLS

Abbreviation	Definition
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
5G	Fifth Generation and Beyond
6G	Sixth Generation
BER	Bit Error Rate
BLER	Block Error Rate
BS	Base Station
CS	Compressed Sensing
ESVC	Enhanced Sparse Vector Coding
FU	Far User
ICI	Inter Carrier Interference
ITS	Intelligent Transportation System
LUT	Look Up Table
MC-NOMA	Multicarrier Non Orthogonal Multiple Access
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
MU	Multi User
MU-SVC	Multiuser-Sparse Vector Coding
NU	Near User
OMP	Orthogonal Matching Pursuit
PER	Packet Error Rate
PoER	Position Error Rate
QPSK	Quadrature Phase Shift Keying
SER	Symbol Error Rate
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SRA	Sparse Recovery Algorithm
ST	Superimposed Transmission
SVC	Sparse Vector Coding
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency communication
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything

devices communicate with each other around the clock and demand high reliability to complete the task [31]–[34]. Thus, URLLC along with spectral efficiency to support massive connectivity is of keen interest in 6G communications. The main aim of this paper is to serve multiple users in single transmission thereby, enhancing the performance of the system. In this paper, multiuser (MU) short packet transmission is enabled through a sparse vector for URLLC. Initially, information of the far user (FU) is encoded into a sparse vector and the near user (NU) information is converted to symbols. Now, the symbols are embedded into the position of non-zero elements in the FU sparse vector. This superimposed signal is pseudo-randomly spread through a code book and transmitted over the channel. At the receiver's end, the support identification is performed through SRA along with sparse demapping and symbol detection in FU and NU, respectively. The key advantage of the proposed multiuser SVC (MU-SVC) scheme over ESVC is that FU and NU can obtain their information by decoding only the non-zero positions and symbols, respectively. Also, optimal power allocation is not required for NU and FU in MU-SVC. Moreover, in this paper position error rate (PoER) and symbol error rate (SER) analyses are performed which shows the proposed scheme is much more reliable with low latency. Furthermore, spectral efficiency, user fairness along with MU connectivity are also achieved for URLLC. For ease of reference, Table I summarizes the list of symbols. The fore-fold contributions of this paper are summarized here:

- A novel spectral efficient MU-SVC transmission scheme for URLLC has been proposed for MU environments.

- It is shown that MU-SVC serves more than one user simultaneously, without any compromise in latency and reliability standards of ESVC.
- A new performance metric viz., PoER has been computed to analyse the reliability of the proposed system and also its significance is discussed.
- Extensive numerical analysis has been carried out for the proposed MU-SVC system by varying the key parameters of SVC and it has been validated through Monte-Carlo simulations.
- Furthermore, bit error rate (BER), complexity and latency analyses are performed for MU-SVC and compared with existing SVC techniques.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the proposed system model with encoding and decoding procedures. The significance of PoER, numerical performance analysis in terms of PoER, SER, BER, and computational complexity are put forth in Section III. Section IV presents the simulation results of the MU-SVC scheme with various key parameters of SVC and a comparison with the existing schemes. Also, the latency concern of MU-SVC is exploited utilizing a timing frame followed by conclusion in Section V.

II. MULTIUSER SPARSE VECTOR CODING

Consider a downlink scenario where multiple users need to be served by the base station (BS) for short packet transmission in URLLC. With the objective of meeting the URLLC target defined by third generation partnership project (3GPP) [11] and striving to attain spectral efficiency while ensuring fairness among users, an MU-SVC scheme is proposed which exploits SVC and superimposed techniques. Multiple users at the receiver end are grouped as FU and NU based on the distance from the base station (BS). Initially, at the BS, FU information is mapped to sparse vector \tilde{s} with sparsity K and sparse vector length N . Now, the NU information is transformed into symbols through modulation techniques and the symbols are embedded into the position of non-zero elements of the FU sparse vector which results in an embedded sparse vector s . The pseudo-code for generation of MU-SVC from FU and NU data is described in Algorithm 1. The number of bits that can be encoded is obtained as $b = \lfloor \log_2 \binom{N}{K} \rfloor$. Subsequently, each sparse vector is spread into m physical resource through pseudo-random spreading. Let the non-zero elements of FU be at the p^{th} and q^{th} positions in which the NU symbols are embedded and its vector is represented mathematically as,

$$x = S_p^{NU} C_p + S_q^{NU} C_q \quad (1)$$

where, S_p^{NU} and S_q^{NU} are the NU symbols at the p^{th} and q^{th} positions. The code book is designed precisely by random Bernoulli distribution with dimension $C = (m \times N)$ in which $m < N$ such that the sensing matrix ($x = Cs$) holds enough information for recovering the sparse vector, where m is the

Algorithm 1 Pseudo-code for the MU-SVC scheme

Input: Length of the sparse vector (N), Number of users (U), FU Information (W), NU symbols (x_U), Sparsity (K)
Output: MU-Sparse vector (s)

Initialisation : $p = 0$

- 1: **for** $a = 2$ to N **do**
- 2: **for** $b = 1$ to $a - 1$ **do**
- 3: **if** $p = (W)$ (Decimal value) **then**
- 4: $\tilde{s} = (2^{(a-1)} + 2^{(b-1)})$ (Binary value)
- 5: **end if**
- 6: $p = p + 1$
- 7: **end for**
- 8: **end for**
- 9: $s = \text{indexmod}[\tilde{s}(x_U)]$
- 10: **return** s

number of resource elements. The random code book matrix can be realized as in (2) with equal probabilities of 1 and -1 .

$$C = \frac{1}{\xi} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & 1 & \ddots & & & \vdots \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & \ddots & & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \cdots & \cdots & -1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}_{(m \times N)} \quad (2)$$

where ξ is the normalization factor based on the modulation technique aided. Conventionally, for symbol encoding M -array quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK) modulation is utilized and its normalization is calculated as $\xi = \sqrt{\frac{2(M+1)}{3}}$ in which M is the order of modulation. After spreading, the sparse signal is transmitted over the Rayleigh channel with independent and identically distributed noise (v) which is expressed as $y = Hx + v$, where H is a diagonal matrix representing the channel coefficients. On the other side, the sparse signal seems to be an undetermined system in nature and requires CS techniques for the detection of non-zero position which turns out to be a determined system.

Fig. 1 sketches the encoding block diagram of the proposed MU-SVC scheme at the BS whereas, Fig. 2 (a) and Fig. 2(b) shows the decoding process of MU-SVC at the FU and NU respectively. At the FU, support identification is carried out through greedy algorithms such as orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) from which the non-zero positions are identified. To aid SRA, it is taken care that $m \leq \mathcal{O}(K \log N)$ for support identification [4]. In OMP, the sparse mapped information is projected onto the sensing matrix and correlation between each column in ϕ is obtained, where $\phi = HC$. The maximum correlation column is considered for each non-zero element and the residual factor is updated in each iteration. The index of the support estimated at p -th iteration is given by,

$$\omega_p = \arg \max_{1 \leq n \leq N} |\langle \phi_n, r^{p-1} \rangle|^2 \quad (3)$$

where r is the residual factor. Once the support ($\hat{\Omega}$) is

Fig. 1. MU-SVC encoding scheme at the BS.

Fig. 2. MU-SVC decoding scheme at (a) FU (b) NU.

TABLE II
MU-SPARSE MAPPING OF USERS INFORMATION FOR
 $K = 2, U = 2, W = 5, N = 9$

FU Information ($b = 5 \text{ bits}$)	MU-Sparse Vectors ($N = 9 \text{ bits}$)
0 0 0 0 0	$x_1^{NU} x_2^{NU} 0 0 0 0 0 0 0$
0 0 0 0 1	$x_1^{NU} 0 x_2^{NU} 0 0 0 0 0 0$
0 0 0 1 0	$0 x_1^{NU} x_2^{NU} 0 0 0 0 0 0$
0 0 0 1 1	$x_1^{NU} 0 0 x_2^{NU} 0 0 0 0 0$
\vdots	\vdots
1 1 1 1 1	$0 0 0 x_1^{NU} 0 0 0 0 x_2^{NU}$

identified, sparse demapping is performed to decode the FU information through look up table (LUT) approach. Likewise, support identification is performed at the NU and symbol detection is computed to decode the information. The main contribution of the MU-SVC is that despite adopting the superimposed principle, each user can decode their information simultaneously. Moreover, power can be concentrated in non-zero positions rather than optimal power allocation for the FU and NU. The allegorical representation of MU-SVC is sketched in Fig. 3 for ease of understanding. Table II displays the mapping of FU and NU data into superimposed sparse vectors for a specific scenario and this can be extended to any number of users and sparse vectors without loss of generality. Fig. 4 portrays the downlink scenario of the proposed MU-SVC scheme for URLLC applications.

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSES OF MU-SVC

In the proposed MU-SVC scheme, it is observed that the non-zero position of the sparse vector corresponds to FU data and embedded symbols in the non-zero position are

Fig. 3. Allegorical representation of MU-SVC.

Fig. 4. Downlink MU-SVC system model.

associated with the NU data. Thus, we study the performance of MU-SVC as two folds viz., PoER and SER, rather than conventional analysis such as BER, BLER, etc. PoER can be defined as the probability of unsuccessful decoding of the exact non-zero positions from the sparse vector. PoER is analyzed for FU as well as NU because both the users need to identify the non-zero position and SER is calculated only for NU which retrieves its information through symbol detection techniques. However, the PoER corresponding to NU does not impact the performance of NU since its information is only the symbols. This paper performs an analysis of PoER and SER without loss of generality, with b bits of information, sparse vector length N , sparsity K and m physical resources.

A. Significance of PoER in MU-SVC

The decoding of FU and NU information involves the identification of non-zero positions and symbol decoding, respectively. To be precise, the non-zero positions replicate the FU information and symbols represent NU data. Since non-zero position decoding is alone sufficient to obtain the FU information, its performance lies upon the number of errors in decoding the non-zero positions. Thus, PoER calculation is required to analyze the FU performance in the MU-SVC scheme. Table IV (Refer to Appendix) shows the sparse mapped vectors at the transmitter and demapped sparse vectors with decoded data at the receiver. All possible combinations

of 5 bit input data for $K = 2$ with a transmit signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of -2 dB are considered for PoER analysis at the FU. It can be observed that for half of the input data combinations, the sparse demapping is done perfectly without error in decoding the non-zero positions. For the remaining input combinations, the exact identification of the non-zero positions is mismatched and in most cases, only a single position is identified to be the error. Also, the significance of PoER is to study the characteristic of SRA on the MU-SVC scheme concerning the error in decoding the position of non-zero elements. In conventional performance analyses such as BLER, packet error rate (PER), etc., even a single position change detected at the receiver leads to an entire sparse vector being the error, thereby degrading the performance of the system. On the other hand, to obtain the NU data, decoding of symbols embedded at the non-zero positions of the sparse vector is required. However, direct symbol detection could not be possible without the identification of the non-zero positions. Thus, initially, the non-zero position is identified and subsequently symbol decoding is performed to obtain the NU information. Similar to Table IV, analyses at the NU can be performed which contributes to less PoER due to the distance factor from the BS. A final note is that performance analysis in terms of PoER shows that the MU-SVC scheme contributes to enhanced reliability than other conventional short packet coding schemes.

B. PoER for FU and NU

We consider the sparsity to be K and the non-zero elements be at the k -th and l -th position such that $\Omega_s = k, l$. Thus, the support (non-zero position) can be defined as $\tilde{s}_\Omega = [\tilde{s}_k, \tilde{s}_l]^T$ where $\tilde{s}_k = \mathfrak{A}_k + j\mathfrak{B}_k$ and $\tilde{s}_l = \mathfrak{A}_l + j\mathfrak{B}_l$, where, \mathfrak{A} and \mathfrak{B} are complex variables. PoER occurs when support is not identified correctly by the SRA and mathematically written as,

$$PoER = P(\Omega_s^* \neq \Omega_{\tilde{s}}). \quad (4)$$

where $\Omega_{\tilde{s}}$ is the exact positions of non-zero elements. OMP performs support detection and the support identified successfully at p -th iteration be I^p , where I is the probability of success and the corresponding probability can be expressed as,

$$P_{success} = 1 - P(\Omega_s^* \neq \Omega_{\tilde{s}}) = P(I^2 | I^1) P(I^1). \quad (5)$$

The NU data is converted to symbols through any type of modulation schemes and the real and imaginary part decisions are taken in first and second iteration, respectively. The conditional probability for identifying the support in first iteration with channel coefficients $h_{FU} = [h_1, h_2, \dots, h_m]^T$ is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} P(I^1 | h_{FU}) &= \prod_{(i=1, i \neq k)}^N P \left(\left| \mathfrak{A} \left\langle \frac{\phi_k}{\|\phi_k\|_2}, r^0 \right\rangle \right| \right) \\ &\geq P \left(\left| \mathfrak{A} \left\langle \frac{\phi_i}{\|\phi_i\|_2}, r^0 \right\rangle \right| \right), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where, r^0 is the initial residual factor. The support estimate at the first iteration is expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{A} \left\langle \frac{\phi_k}{\|\phi_k\|_2}, r^0 \right\rangle &= \mathfrak{A} \left\langle \frac{\phi_k}{\|\phi_k\|_2}, \phi_k \tilde{s}_k + \phi_l \tilde{s}_l + \nu \right\rangle \\ &= \mathfrak{A}_k \|h_{FU}\|_2 + \mathfrak{A}_l \mu_{kl} \|h_{FU}\|_2 + z_r. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The term μ_{kl} mutual coherence is the maximum correlation between c_k and c_l , where c_k and c_l are code book vector at k -th and l -th estimates. The terms \mathfrak{A}_k and \mathfrak{A}_l are the real part variables at k -th and l -th estimates, $z_r = \mathfrak{A} \left(\frac{\phi_k^T}{\|\phi_k\|_2} \nu \right)$. Likewise, we have

$$\mathfrak{A} \left\langle \frac{\phi_i}{\|\phi_i\|_2}, r^0 \right\rangle = \mathfrak{A}_k \mu_{ik} \|h_{FU}\|_2 + \mathfrak{A}_l \mu_{il} \|h_{FU}\|_2 + z_i. \quad (8)$$

where, $z_i = \mathfrak{A} \left(\frac{\phi_i^T}{\|\phi_i\|_2} \nu \right)$. Now, utilising $P(|A| \geq |B|) = P(A > |B|) P(A > 0) + P(-A > |B|) P(A < 0)$ in (7) and (8), the conditional probability of the estimate is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} P \left(\left| \mathfrak{A} \left\langle \frac{\phi_k}{\|\phi_k\|_2}, r^0 \right\rangle \right| \geq \left| \mathfrak{A} \left\langle \frac{\phi_i}{\|\phi_i\|_2}, r^0 \right\rangle \right| \right) \\ = P \left(\left| (\mathfrak{A}_k + \mathfrak{A}_l \mu_{kl}) \|h_{FU}\|_2 + z_r \right| \geq \left| (\mathfrak{A}_k \mu_{ik} + \mathfrak{A}_l \mu_{il}) \|h_{FU}\|_2 + z_i \right| \right). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The Q function criteria, $P(z_k < -\|h\|_2) = 1 - Q \left(-\frac{\|h\|_2}{\frac{\sigma_\nu}{\sqrt{2}}} \right) \geq 1 - \exp \left(-\frac{\|h\|_2^2}{\sigma_\nu^2} \right)$ is used for further simplification of (9) and the support estimate is rewritten as,

$$\begin{aligned} P \left(\left| \mathfrak{A} \left\langle \frac{\phi_k}{\|\phi_k\|_2}, r^0 \right\rangle \right| \right) &\geq \\ 1 - \exp \left(-\frac{\|h_{FU}\|_2^2 \zeta_1}{2\sigma_\nu^2} \right) - \exp \left(-\frac{\|h_{FU}\|_2^2 \eta_1}{\sigma_\nu^2} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where, σ_ν^2 is the noise variance, $\zeta_1 = \{\mathfrak{A}_k + \mathfrak{A}_l \mu^* - (|\mathfrak{A}_k| + |\mathfrak{A}_l|) \mu^*\}^2$ and $\eta_1 = \{\mathfrak{A}_k + \mathfrak{A}_l \mu^*\}^2$ in which μ^* is the absolute value of the maximum correlation between two columns of Φ . Furthermore, the probability of support at the first iteration with realization of FU channel gain is expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} P(I^1) &= \\ \int P(I^1 | h_{FU}) f_{h_{FU}}(x) dx &= E_h [P(I^1 | h_{FU})]. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

On simplification, by $E_h \left[\exp \left(-\frac{\|h\|_2^2}{\sigma_\nu^2} \right) \right] = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sigma_\nu^2} \right)^{-m}$ [4], the first iteration support estimate is expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} P(I^1) &\geq \\ \left(1 - \left(1 + \frac{\zeta_1}{2\sigma_\nu^2} \right)^{-m} - \left(1 + \frac{\eta_1}{\sigma_\nu^2} \right)^{-m} \right)^{N-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Similarly, the success of second iteration can be derived and expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} P(I^2) &\geq \\ \left(1 - \left(1 + \frac{\zeta_2}{2\sigma_\nu^2} \right)^{-m} - \left(1 + \frac{\eta_2}{\sigma_\nu^2} \right)^{-m} \right)^{N-2}, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $\zeta_2 = \{\mathfrak{B}_l - |\mathfrak{B}_l| \mu^*\}^2$ and $\eta_2 = \mathfrak{B}_l^2$. Finally, the closed form expression of PoER for both the iteration can be written as,

$$PoER_{FU} \geq 1 - \left(1 - \left(1 + \frac{\zeta_1}{2\sigma_\nu^2} \right)^{-m} - \left(1 + \frac{\eta_1}{\sigma_\nu^2} \right)^{-m} \right)^{N-1} \times \left(1 - \left(1 + \frac{\zeta_2}{2\sigma_\nu^2} \right)^{-m} - \left(1 + \frac{\eta_2}{\sigma_\nu^2} \right)^{-m} \right)^{N-2}. \quad (14)$$

The PoER of the NU is same as that of FU with the only difference being realization of the NU channel gain (h_{NU}).

C. SER for NU

The NU adopts symbol detection techniques to decode its information and SER occurs if the detected symbol is incorrect. Assuming the transmitted symbol to be \tilde{S}_k and incorrect symbol as $\tilde{S}_{\bar{k}}$, the pair wise error probability is expressed in terms of Q function [35] as,

$$P(\tilde{s}_k \rightarrow \tilde{s}_{\bar{k}} | y, h_{NU}) = Q \left(\sqrt{\frac{\|\phi_i(\tilde{s}^k - \tilde{s}^l)\|^2}{2\sigma_\nu^2}} \right). \quad (15)$$

Now, the channel is realized and minimum Euclidean distance (d_{min}) among the symbols are considered with NU channel gain. Using $Q(x) \leq \exp(-\frac{x^2}{2})$, (15) can be simplified and written as,

$$SER_{NU} \leq k \left(1 + \frac{\mu^* d_{min}^2}{4\sigma_\nu^2} \right)^{-m}. \quad (16)$$

Thus, the final expression for SER at NU has been obtained in which the resource allocation plays a vital role in deciding the SER performance. The numerical expressions of PoER and SER are validated with Monte Carlo simulation over Rayleigh fading channel in the next section and the performance of the MU-SVC scheme is analyzed with various key parameters.

D. BER for MU-SVC and ESVC

The BER analysis is performed to enact the performance gain of MU-SVC over the ESVC scheme. The BER can be analyzed similarly to BLER in [9]. It is defined as the number of bits received as an error in the total number of bits transmitted. The probability of unsuccessful decoding can be obtained by $BER = 1 - P_{success}$ for both FU and NU with their respective channel coefficients. In the case of ESVC, both the users need to perform support detection as well as symbol decoding to decode their information. To calculate BER, the detected symbols are converted to bits. On the other hand in MU-SVC, the FU performs only support detection to decode its information from the non-zero positions, whereas, NU is concerned only with symbol decoding. The BER performance for the MU-SVC and ESVC schemes are traced out in Section IV.

TABLE III
COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS

User	ESVC	MU-SVC
NU	$\rho_p + \rho_{SD}$	$\rho_p + \rho_{SD}$
	$IKN + S_K$	$IKN + S_K$
FU	$\rho_p + \rho_{SD}$	ρ_p
	$IKN + S_K$	IKN

E. Complexity Analysis

The complexity analysis is performed by considering the process of decoding the non-zero positions and symbols as ρ_p and ρ_{SD} respectively, for ultra-short packet transmission. In the case of ESVC, the support identification (ρ_p) and symbol decoding (ρ_{SD}) has to be done by each user individually to obtain their information. Whereas in the proposed scheme, the FU performs only support identification (ρ_p) and the NU undergoes both processes ($\rho_p + \rho_{SD}$). Thus, the complexity at the NU for the proposed MU-SVC is the operation of ($U \times (IKN + S_K)$). Likewise, the complexity at the FU is only to detect the non-zero position which is $U \times (IKN)$, where I is the number of iteration SRA takes for convergence, U is the number of users and S_K is the K number of symbol detection process. Thus, as a system, the complexity of the proposed MU-SVC lies in performing the operation of $U \times ((IKN)^2 + S_K)$. Whereas, in ESVC complexity lies in detecting the non-zero positions and decoding the symbols for each user which is $U \times (IKN + S_K)$. Similarly, in case of SVC the complexity is to detect the non-zero positions alone i.e., $U \times (IKN)$. Even though it seems that the complexity of SVC is less than MU-SVC, the amount of information transmitted, number of users served and reliability are much higher with less latency than former. Table III shows the complexity analyses for MU-SVC and ESVC schemes for the MU environment in terms of decoding at the user end. Inference shows that the MU-SVC requires less computation, thereby achieving less complexity with reduced latency than the ESVC scheme.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, the key results are presented for MU-SVC in terms of transmitting SNR versus PoER and SER. For simulation, the parameters are assigned to $N = 96, b = 5, m = 88, K = 2, \mu^* \approx 0.6$ and the distance of FU is twice as that of NU. In Fig. 5, the performance in terms of PoER for FU and NU is traced out with the upper bound. It is observed that NU performs better than FU due to the distance factor and on an average 2 dB gain is obtained by NU when compared with FU to achieve a PoER greater than 10^{-2} . Also, the simulation result well matches with upper bound analytical values. Further, it is evident that the system is very reliable even at low SNR values due to the sparse nature of the information and CS-based decoding techniques. The NU performs symbol detection in addition to support identification and its analysis is shown in Fig. 6 and 7. The simulation values are evaluated with numerical in Fig. 6 and observed that as SNR increases the SER attained is low which means the

Fig. 5. PoER MC simulation and numerical validation of MU-SVC.

Fig. 7. MU-SVC SER for NU with various information bits.

Fig. 6. MU-SVC SER performance of NU with numerical validation.

Fig. 8. MU-SVC PoER performance with various resource allocation.

probability of symbol decoding success is high. Furthermore, SER for various input information bits is analyzed in Fig. 7 which shows that the SER and number of information are directly proportional to each other. This is because as the amount of information to be encoded is more, the length of the sparse vector gets increased which leads to a higher decoding error.

The PoER performance analysis of FU and NU with various resource allocations ($m = 28, 88, 148, 296$) is shown in Fig. 8 with $N = 320$. Observation reveals that as the resources or sensing matrix is of higher order, the PoER probability is very low, since there are enough measurements to decode the symbol correctly. To be precise, if the measurement changes from 28 to 88, a gain of 3 dB and 4 dB in FU and NU, respectively are obtained. Moreover, it is observed that the reliability of the MU-SVC scheme is very high, and low latency can be achieved with less iteration.

In Fig. 9, the SNR versus PoER plot for various input

information bits ($b = 4, 5, 8, 10$) is analyzed for FU and NU over the Rayleigh fading channel. Investigation shows if the input information is increased for the same amount of measurements, the performance of the MU-SVC scheme is poor for both the users. However, as b increases, the performance can be enhanced if the bandwidth constraint is neglected. Since the sparsity is high (less number of non-zero elements), support is identified in less iteration through greedy algorithms. Also, it is evident that the input bits and PoER are proportional to each other with a fixed resource.

The performance of MU-SVC concerning various sparse vector size ($N = 9, 24, 48, 64, 96$) are analyzed and plotted in Fig. 10. From the result, it is clear that the error rate depends on sparse vector size for a specific measurement but the performance is not affected as in case of varying the resource. As N gets high, there is a marginal difference in PoER for FU as well as NU. A final note is that the MU-SVC scheme provides ultra-reliability even in a very low SNR regime due

Fig. 9. MU-SVC PoER performance with various information bits.

Fig. 11. BER performance of MU-SVC with existing SVC schemes.

Fig. 10. MU-SVC PoER performance with various sparse vector length.

Fig. 12. Spectral analysis of existing SVC schemes and MU-SVC.

to the sparse nature of the information transmitted. Also, decoding involves only position identification and support with symbol detection for FU and NU, respectively. Thus, MU-SVC provides low latency with less system complexity in MU scenario.

Fig. 11 traces the BER plot of MU-SVC with ESVC and SVC schemes for various transmit SNR with $K = 2$, $m = 5$, $N = 10$ and the distance of FU from the BS is twice as that of NU. Immediate inference is that for all the schemes BER decreases as SNR gets high and the FU performance is comparatively less than NU due to the distance factor. Keen observation discloses that the performance of MU-SVC is superior to ESVC and SVC for both the users. In MU-SVC, the FU performs only support identification to decode its information and thus possesses a gain of 2 dB for BER of 10^{-3} over the ESVC scheme which requires support identification as well as symbol detection. In the case of NU, both the schemes perform support identification and symbol detection to decode their information, but the NU of the MU-SVC shows less BER. This is because the information of NU

depends only on the symbols and not on non-zero positions, and hence the support identification error is neglected. In case of SVC, the performance depends on decoding of non-zero positions alone, yet its error rate is higher than ESVC and MU-SVC due to symbol decoding process, which contributes for less error than position decoding. Thus, the MU-SVC provides user fairness without optimal power allocation to the users and more efficient than ESVC and SVC schemes for the MU scenario.

Moreover, the spectral analysis is computed in terms of time slots required for users to make successful communication. Fig. 12 shows the spectral occupancy for SVC, ESVC and MU-SVC schemes, in the MU environment. For ultra-short packet transmission, the SVC and ESVC requires individual time slots to serve each user, Whereas, MU-SVC serves more than one user simultaneously in a single time frame. Thus, the proposed MU-SVC scheme is spectral efficient and serves more users simultaneously than ESVC and SVC schemes. Finally, the latency is evaluated for the proposed scheme and compared with ESVC and SVC schemes. Latency is calculated

Fig. 13. Latency probability distribution of existing SVC schemes and MU-SVC.

from the time of initial transmission to the successful decoding of information at the end user. Fig. 13 plots the latency probability distribution of MU-SVC, ESVC and SVC schemes for achieving error rate of 10^{-5} at a transmit SNR of -2 dB for $N = 96, b = 5, m = 88, K = 2, U = 2$ and $\mu^* \approx 0.6$. The analysis is carried out with re-transmission (repetition) till successful decoding for both NU and FU scenario. Inference of the distribution reveals that the latency of the proposed MU-SVC scheme is much smaller than the conventional schemes i.e., on an average 15% and 34% than ESVC and SVC schemes, respectively. This is because, both the users need to perform support detection and symbol decoding in the ESVC and SVC schemes which requires more latency than MU-SVC scheme. Also, it is observed that the proposed MU-SVC decodes the information successfully within $1ms$, thereby contributing to URLLC with spectral efficacy which supports for ITS in 5GB communications.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a novel MU-SVC scheme, for the transmission of ultra-short packets in URLLC that aids for ITS. The FU information is mapped into a sparse vector and the NU information are converted into symbols and embedded into the non-zero position of the FU sparse vector. The decoding of the sparse vector is done through SRA and sparse demapping in FU, whereas SRA with symbol detection technique is adopted in NU. From the numerical and simulation results of PoER and SER, it is demonstrated that our proposed MU-SVC scheme achieves the reliability and latency standards of 6G at the low SNR regime itself. The MU-SVC performance is analyzed by varying the key parameters and it is proved that the proposed scheme serves multiple users without sacrificing the reliability standard. Also, the significance of PoER performance in MU-SVC is elaborated for FU and NU. Furthermore, BER, complexity, spectral and latency analyses prove that the proposed

MU-SVC outperforms the SVC and ESVC schemes. Thus, the proposed MU-SVC scheme is shown to be a strong candidate for URLLC scenarios with high spectral efficiency for ultra-short packet transmission in ITS applications.

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APPENDIX
TABLE I
SIGNIFICANCE OF POER IN MU-SPARSE MAPPING OF USERS INFORMATION FOR
 $K = 2, U = 2, W = 5, SNR = -2 \text{ dB}$

Data	Sparse Mapping	Support Detection	Sparse Demapping	No. of error in position	No. of errors in bits
00000	1100000000	0100001000	10000	1	1
00001	1010000000	1010000000	00001	0	0
00010	0110000000	0101000000	00100	1	2
00011	1001000000	1000100000	00110	1	1
00100	0101000000	0000011000	10100	2	1
00101	0011000000	0011000000	00101	0	0
00110	1000100000	0000110000	01110	1	1
00111	0100100000	0100010000	01011	1	2
01000	0010100000	0010100000	01000	0	0
01001	0001100000	0001100000	01001	0	0
01010	1000010000	1000001000	01111	1	2
01011	0100010000	0000010100	11010	1	2
01100	0010010000	0010010000	01100	0	0
01101	0001010000	0001000010	11000	1	3
01110	0000110000	0000110000	01110	0	0
01111	1000001000	1000001000	01111	0	0
10000	0100001000	0000101000	10011	2	2
10001	0010001000	0010001000	10001	0	0
10010	0001001000	0001001000	10010	0	0
10011	0000101000	0000101000	10011	0	0
10100	0000011000	0000101000	10011	1	3
10101	1000000010	1000000001	11100	1	2
10110	0100000010	0100000010	10110	0	0
10111	0010000010	1000100000	00110	2	2
11000	0001000010	1000000010	10101	1	3
11001	0000100010	0000100010	11001	0	0
11010	0000010010	0000010010	11010	0	0
11011	0000001010	0000001010	11011	0	0
11100	1000000001	1000000010	10101	1	2
11101	0100000001	0100010000	01011	1	3
11110	0010000001	0010000001	11110	0	0
11111	0001000001	0010000010	10111	2	1